

Effectiveness of Enterprise Resource Planning System in Mining Company

By

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DECLARATION FORM

The work I have submitted is my effort. I certify that all the material in this Research project, which is not my work, has been identified and acknowledged. No materials are included for which a degree has been previously conferred upon me.

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Date 06/July,2016

ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the enterprise resource planning system using the Dangote Cement factory in Obajana- Nigeria as a case study. The justification for this location was provided in the study.

Relevant literature on the benefits of ERP and the implementation challenge was reviewed to develop a robust approach to the impact of ERP in the mining industry. It is evident in this study that effective deployment of ERP will streamline the complex manual mining process. Strategic alignment of business needs is required for ERP to yield the desired result. Organizational needs must be clearly understood before ERP is aligned to provide solutions to mining challenges.

Some of the challenges that mining companies faced were discussed. Research questions were crafted to validate the impact of ERP in the mining sector.

The conceptual framework of ERP was discussed using existing theories from different authors. It is obvious from the literature reviewed that the information that was fragmented before the advent of ERP has been centralized with effective integration with all the departments in the organization. The role and implementation of ERP was discussed. ERP effectiveness was discussed using some critical indicators. It is evident from the research that the effectiveness of IT innovation depends on the impact on the organization's goals and objectives.

The research methodology used for this study is qualitative given the quest of the researcher to provide in-depth analysis on the study. The interview was conducted using four persons from different departments to provide an unbiased assessment of the impact of ERP in their organization. The data collected was analyzed with grounded theory using NVivo software for analysis. This software made it possible to have a deep understanding and assessment of this IT innovation. Ethical concerns and safeguard issues were discussed for participants to have confidence in their anonymity and for them to know that the study was an academic exercise.

From the analyzed result, it is evident that the adoption of ERP brought a marginal increase in the production of cement in Dangote. However, there was an initial decline in organization performance within a few months of adoption because the management team did not sensitize other staff on the adoption of ERP. It is evident that the adoption of ERP has brought about real-time information to guide management teams in strategic decision-making

There are some limitations concerning the sample and the data used for evaluation.

The sample includes a large mining company (Dangote Cement Factory). Future research could use smaller mining companies to evaluate. Consequently, an effort should be made in the future to use a mining company that has not deployed ERP as a control organization with another mining company that has deployed ERP. This will provide a better comparison model to evaluate effectiveness. The geographical location of this study is Nigeria in Africa, it may not have wide acceptance in other continents where there are varying organizational cultures.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Acknowledgement.....	7
Chapter 1: Introduction, organizational context, and research objectives	
1.1 Background Information.....	8
1.2 Statement of the problem.....	10
1.3 Research questions.....	11
1.4 Objectives of the study.....	11
1.5 Scope of the study.....	12
1.6 Potential benefits.....	13
1.7 Conclusion.....	13
Chapter 2: Literature Review	
2.1 Conceptual Framework.....	15
2.2 Role of ERP.....	17
2.3 Benefits of ERP.....	18
2.4 ERP Implementation.....	19
2.5 ERP Effectiveness.....	21
2.6 Assessing ERP Effectiveness.....	23
2.7 Literature gaps.....	24
2.8 Conclusion.....	25
Chapter 3: Research Methodology	
3.1 Data Collection.....	26
3.2 Case Study.....	26
3.3 Subject of case study.....	27
3.4 Data Sampling.....	28
3.5 Design of interview schedule.....	28
3.6 Data Analysis.....	29
3.7 Data Reliability and Validity.....	30
3.8 Ethical Concerns and Safeguards.....	30

3.9 Conclusion.....	31
Chapter 4: Analysis and Interpretation.	
4.1 Qualitative Data Analysis & Interpretation	33
4.2 Conclusion	40
Chapter 5: Discussion and Conclusion.....	42
5.1 Summary of major findings.....	42
5.2 Managerial Implications.....	43
5.3 Suggestions for Management in Other Mining Companies.....	44
5.4 Limitation & Area of Future Research.....	44
5.5 Conclusion.....	45
References.....	46

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background Information

The pace of technological progress and change has become so fierce in recent years that organization needs to respond quickly to new environmental challenges and need to continuously renew their technological capacity, particularly in information technology to ensure their prosperity and sustainability (Gera & Gu, 2004:39). It is believed that for any organization to succeed and survive, they need to depend on creativity, innovation and discovery (Martins & Terblanche, 2008:45). The management team of the organization must focus on how to unleash creativity and potentials of their employee. They must create working conditions that will enhance innovative change for sustainable competitive advantage.

Organizational culture plays a critical in the creativity and innovation that occur in every organization (Johnson, 1996:10)

ERP is one of the rapidly developed IT innovative concepts in mining organizations. Many companies have embraced ERP innovation while others are in the process of implementing an ERP system (Zhe Zang, et al., 2004:60). Some organizations are reluctant to invest huge capital in an ERP system that may not translate to a proportional increase in production.

It is believed that strategic implementation of enterprise resource planning systems improves organization effectiveness (T. Davenport, 2001:128). The complexity and intangible benefits made it difficult to evaluate the effectiveness of ERP in the mining sector (Jen-Her Wu, 2006:890). Measurement of ERP effectiveness is a process that could be guidelines for managers to find the weaknesses and optimal use of the system to align with organizational objectives

According to Goni (2012:215), the ability to measure in advance the effectiveness of enterprise resource planning will guide the organization in their investment and deployment to meet their business needs for sustainable strategic advantage. Such organizations will be careful in the selection of ERP to meet their needs. It is evident to the researcher that effectiveness could be measured in line with the organization's goals and deliverables.

Some mining companies embrace technological change to streamline their business process and sustain a competitive edge while others are reluctant to take the risk on huge investments that may not translate to a proportional increase in profit. It has been a great concern to some Chief Executives in mining companies on how the complex mining activities could be streamlined to enhance competitive edge.

The emphasis on supply chain management and the advancement of information technology created a need for enterprise-wide integration. Some organization believes that Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) has become a “must have” system for every firm to improve competitiveness (Hsiuju Rebecca Yen, Chewn Sheu, 2003:210). The quest for real-time information from the management team has inspired many companies to embrace ERP innovation.

For mining companies to thrive and have a competitive edge, they need to manage and optimize an increasingly complex supply chain with automation that will streamline their operational process. Leading mining companies know that operational excellence is key to operational challenges (SAP, 2014:11). “But too often manual processes, various equipment and systems, and information delays make it difficult to control costs, streamline business activities, create efficiencies, and make the right business decisions promptly to achieve competitive advantage” (SAP, 2014:12).

The advent of ERP has revolutionized the mining industry with the analytical tool that identifies trends and patterns in areas such as operations and profitability, which can help improve business decisions. “With ERP solutions, mining companies can realize a fast return on investment and reduce IT spending by standardizing software on a single platform” (SAP, 2014:11).

A comprehensive ERP solution provides the functionality to help a mining company address these aspects systematically and thereby drive operational excellence (SAP, 2014:18).

According to Kumar, (2000:24) ERP involves the seamless integration of processes across functional areas such as finance, human resources, manufacturing, and logistics. ERP system has a different configurable module that integrates all the activities in departments into a centralized database (Kumer, 2000:24). Mining operations can be tracked using real-time information that will guide management in strategic decision-making.

1.2 Statement of the Problem:

Some of the challenges facing mining companies include the huge cost of the manual mining process, equipment complexity across the facility, and the inability to predict supplier and customer demands. (SAP, 2014:18). It is critical for mining organizations to align their organization needs with IT innovation that will enhance their organization's performance while reducing costs by enhancing operational efficiency.

An organization must identify its needs so that an IT solution can be strategically provided. Organizational needs must be identified and communicated to the stakeholders that will participate in the organization's performance.

This study related to the following research problems:

- Managing and optimizing complex supply chains in the mining industry is a daunting challenge. Many mining companies in Nigeria cannot optimize the huge deposit of mineral resources following their inability to embrace the innovative technology of automation that could leverage on their great potentials. The complexity of the mining processing makes it difficult for a management team to track the activities in the industry.
- Another challenge for manual mining processing is inconsistent data. “But too often manual processes, various equipment and systems, and information delays make it difficult to control cost, streamline business activities, create efficiencies, and make the right business decisions promptly to achieve competitive advantage” (SAP, 2014:10).
- The current demand for Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) implementation is growing fast, but only a few companies have been able to align their business needs with IT innovation. The issues that militate against the effective implementation of ERP have been a great concern to many people in the mining industry.
- Few studies about the impact of ERP systems have reported successful performance improvement, and several areas of ERP systems such as the ability to provide real-time information to customers, reduced production cycle, and on-time completion rates have been reported (Shih-Wen Chien, 2007:55). Some of the massive investment in IT innovation like ERP has not translated to a proportional increase in return on investment.

1.3 Research Questions

To achieve the goal of this study, it is imperative to ascertain the impact of enterprise resource planning in mining using some critical indicators. The indicator shown below will determine whether the organization had optimized ERP or misalignment of IT integration to organization needs.

Does the ERP solution improve productivity in Mining Companies in Nigeria?

What are the issues that militate the practical implementation of ERP in Mining?

Does ERP implementation help management in strategic decision-making?

To measure the impact of ERP solutions in the mining company, it is imperative to determine the performance of the mining company before and after ERP implementation. What is the percentage increase in production? Has the mining company been able to meet up with its production target with the advent of ERP?

There are critical issues that militate against the effective implementation of ERP in a mining company. Some of the issues identified include the huge cost of ERP deployment, inadequate skills of some ERP vendors, resistance due to the organization's existing culture to innovative change, lack of support from top management executives, and integration challenges. How can these issues be mitigated so that mining companies can fully optimize ERP benefits?

It has been a great concern to many stakeholders in the mining industry on the need to invest huge financial capital in ERP deployment. Is it true that ERP Implementation helps the organization by providing information for a strategic decision? Does ERP deployment provide real-time information that contributes to enhanced decision-making?

These pertinent questions will help the researcher to validate his claim on ERP solutions. However, it's believed that there are challenges militating deployment.

1.4 Objective of the Study.

To proffer a solution to the above problems, this study tries to achieve the following objectives:

□ To evaluate the effectiveness of enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems in a mining company in Nigeria. To validate this claim on ERP effectiveness, the researcher critically analyzed the impact of ERP on production and strategic decisions in the organization. Some critical indicators like an increase in production, an increase in sales/profit of the organization, enhanced strategic decision making, and organization process will be analyzed in this study using in-depth interviews to obtain the perception of staff on ERP deployment.

□ To determine some of the challenges that impede effective ERP deployment. The choice of ERP selection and the huge cost of ERP deployment were identified as challenges that impede implementation. There have been few studies in this context looking at the challenges of ERP and the potential benefits of Enterprise Resource Planning implementation. A comprehensive approach to ERP systems in mining companies has been focused on in this study so that mining organizations can be guided at the planning, design, and implementation stages.

An attempt has been made in this research to identify how ERP system manages the functional area of the mining industry; how they fit into the mining value chain, IT requirements with perceived benefits, and the gap between ERP capabilities and the mining sector business needs.

1.5 Scope of the study.

To effectively carry out this work, an effort has been made to check existing theories on the application of ERP in a mining company. Some of the literature reviewed provided background information on the potential benefits of ERP applications. It has helped to refine the topic and also identify the knowledge gap in the area of interest so that the study can contribute to the body of knowledge.

This study focused on the effectiveness of ERP in the mining industry using Dangote Cement in Obajana-Nigeria as the case study. This is the largest Cement factory in Africa and one of the largest in the world with the capacity to produce 12.25 million metric tons per annum.

One organization was used to validate the claim on the effectiveness of ERP. The data obtained may not be a true reflection of small mining companies. However, effort should be made in the future to use a mining company that has not deployed ERP as a control company and also select a company that has deployed ERP so that the impact of ERP can be measured appropriately.

Another limitation observed in this study is that the researcher used only primary data from the interview conducted and no reference was made to secondary data like quarterly production reports which could have provided a robust assessment of ERP in a mining company.

Consequently, the geographical location of this project may not provide wide acceptance given the varying organizational culture. The organizational culture of Dangote Cement in Nigeria may not be the same in other countries which may translate to limited acceptance.

1.6 Potential Benefits of the Study:

This study will give benefits to the mining industry and also the researcher by:

Providing an opportunity for the mining company on how to explore the huge benefits of ERP and also enlighten them on the need to streamline complex mining activities using ERP system.

This study will create awareness of the huge benefits of ERP to the mining company.

This study will provide an academic reference for other researchers who are willing to undertake a similar study.

It's a great opportunity for the researcher to identify gaps in previous research work and contribute to the body of knowledge.

1.7 Conclusion:

This chapter introduced the concept of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) as a required system in a mining company to streamline the complex chain in mining processing. Some of the challenges of the manual mining process were highlighted as problems that impede the effective deployment of ERP to proffer solutions which was captured in the study objectives of the study. The scope of the study was clearly stated looking at the impact of ERP in mining companies using Dangote Cement in Obajana-Nigeria as a case study. This is the largest Cement factory in Africa and one of the largest in the world. The limitation of this study was stated given future research. It was identified that since the case study is a large mining company, some of the data provided may not be relevant for a small mining company. Consequently, it is believed that to provide a robust report; the researcher should use secondary data to complement the primary data source obtained from the interview.

The potential benefit of this research as a contribution to the body of knowledge was discussed. It is believed that this study will provide an academic reference for people that will like to undertake similar research. Some of the relevant literature will be discussed in the next chapter to develop a robust approach to the impact of ERP in the mining sector.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Framework of ERP

Before the advent of ERP, some mining companies were using patchwork software to track their mining activities (SAP, 2014:12). Patchwork provides customized and off-the-shelf software to mining companies (SAP, 2014:12). The challenge of patchwork software is that the information provided is fragmented and not centralized.

With the advent of the ERP system, information that was previously fragmented in many different systems is stored in a single comprehensive data repository where it can be used by many various parts of the business (Laudon, 2013). Because processes were handled on a single platform, decision-makers get a single, unified view of key performance indicators (SAP, 2014:11). "It is believed that ERP systems are packaged software applications that support organization needs looking at the process and structure which are imperative for organization performance (Kumar et al. 2000:39).

Modern ERP systems serve as the foundation for a broad range of e-business models within different companies as well as throughout the value chain (Davenport, 2001:120). Such cross-organizational ERP implementations enable coordination and collaboration among multiple companies in a value network by automating process workflows, and data control flow shared by the partnering businesses (Davenport, 2001:119). The ERP systems deployed by networked businesses are also referred to as ERP II (Bradford et al. 2003:115). Traditionally, 'ERP I' systems focus on the integration of back-office information systems given to one company in a geographical location; while ERP II focuses on linking the company to both customers and vendors which could be extended to a remote office in a different location.(Weston (Jr) 2003:55). For small and medium business mining companies ERP I appear to be preferred while for large-scale mining with a network of mining plants will prefer ERP II. It is evident to the researcher that ERP II will be appropriate for a large mining company with two or more remote locations. Gupta et al. (2000:115) "showed that existing models of information system success are geared towards ERP I and may not be entirely appropriate for measuring ERP II success, as ERP II systems are more complex to measure."

There are more conflicting priorities of stakeholders' interest in ERP II projects than what we have in ERP I which has few stakeholders to coordinate (Davenport et al. 2001:120).

- Identification and quantification of benefits are more challenging and complex for ERP II than for ERP I and IS projects (Venkatraman et al. 1998).
- Extended benefit payback periods make the management and assessment of an ERP very challenging.
- ERP II systems are more complicated than ERP I systems, therefore making implementation more prone to failure (Ferrario et al. 2004:34).

According to Shang (2002:281), the literature reviewed provided background information for a conceptual framework intended to proffer solutions to some of the identified research gaps.

“From a theoretical viewpoint, the objective is to (i) provide a potential benefit of ERP in mining literature and (ii) understand which published work makes what kind of contribution, where they overlap and where they are complementing each other” (Shang et al's, 2002: 280). The practical implications of the framework are visible throughout the ERP implementation.

Shang, (2002:280) suggested that “the conceptual framework can provide an opportunity to explore the relationship between the benefits and the huge costs required to realize ERP system in mining. Because these costs are revealed only later in the ERP lifecycle, thinking of them upfront in the early project stages may help ERP adapters identify risks for budget overruns (Shang, 2002:283). During the ERP implementation, the framework and its associated guidelines provide the adopter with a work plan geared towards realizing organizational goals. (Kaplan,1993). At the after-implementation time, the framework can be used as a checklist to assess the project's success.

To create a framework that is acceptable for cross-organizational collaborations, It is imperative to extend benefit framework with the huge cost required to provide logistics for efficient deployment (Cruijssen et al. 2007:245; Mentzer et al. 2000:199). The huge cost of ERP might not yield the desired result if there is a selection error.

2.2 The Role of ERP.

Enterprise Resource Planning system was defined as a unified system database for the various system modules that all data and processes within organizations had been integrated by using multiple components of computer software and hardware to achieve the integration (Umble, 2003:241).

It is also a software solution that addresses the enterprise needs taking the process view of an organization and in terms of industry Enterprise Resource Planning is a set of activities that support by multi-module application software that manages all the parts of the business (Umble, 2003:243).

Enterprise Resource Planning system works by integrating the whole business information, allowing organizations to manage effectively their resources of people, materials, and finance (Markus et al., 2000). ERP also implements and automates business processes, putting them into a useful format that been standardized across the organization. If ERP is used correctly, it can be an effective management tool (Umble, 2003:244).

The waves of change brought by ERPs have begun to be felt and appreciated by organizations worldwide (Siriginidi Subba Rao, 2000:86). In the past few years, ERP has become a “must have” system for almost every firm to improve competitiveness. Today, over 60% of companies have installed or plan to install a packaged ERP system (Hsiuju Rebecca Yen, Chewn Sheu, 2003).

The advent of ERP has revolutionized the manual way of carrying out the mining process in some parts of developed countries. Some of the mining companies that have superlative performance know that operational excellence is imperative to addressing mining challenges (SAP, 2014:12).

The manual processing, different equipment, and systems and information delays make it difficult to control costs, streamline business activities, create efficiencies, and make the right business decisions promptly to achieve competitive advantage.

Reliable analytical tools are required to identify trends and patterns in areas such as operations and profitability in mining companies, which can help improve business decisions

2.3 Benefits of ERP

The benefits of implementing an Enterprise Resource Planning system are plenty.

An ERP solution can drive operational efficiency and profitability. Having SAP ERP in place helps promote collaboration among different departments, such as finance, logistics, mining, processing, maintenance, and inventory management (SAP, 2014:11). Moreover, with the solution, mining companies can centralize control over operations, reduce redundancies in back-office and logistics processes, and establish shared-services centers to support processes, such as human resources and finance (SAP, 2014:12).

ERP is focused on customers, at this moment providing prompt service delivery. ERP allows open communication among suppliers, vendors, customers, and all other facets of the business (Umble, 2003:244)

Enterprise Resource Planning system can improve business performance in organizations by implementing an efficient planning resource that will synchronize the planning of all processes through organizations (Koh et al., 2007:260).

Enterprise Resource Planning system can modify the business structure and provide successful ingredients required to gain competitive advantages within the organizations (Koh et al., 2007:260).

According to Al-Mashari et al. (2006:359) determining the potential benefits from an ERP implementation is not an easy task. Most of the potential benefits are derived from various ways the system can be implemented and used

The researcher believes that some mining companies have been able to explore the huge benefits of ERP systems in their production, while others are reluctant to take the risk of ERP innovation.

ERP Systems make it easier to track the workflow across various departments, and they reduce the operational costs required in manually tracking and (perhaps) duplicating data using individual & disparate systems (SAP, 2014:12).

2.4 ERP Implementation

ERPs are considered painful to implement because they force an organization to change its way of working as well as they are a considerable expense, with a long return on investment value (Al-Mashari et al., 2003). It is believed that the complexity of an ERP mining company requires a vendor that understands clearly the internal process of integration. It is usually challenging for some staff to learn new skills that will enable them to optimize the ERP deployed.

Careful selection of ERP is required to efficiently deploy it in an organization.

Organizational needs and objectives must be clearly understood before selecting ERP for implementation. The success of ERP implementation has a variety of factors that are considered to be critical and many kinds of research are trying to list them. Al-Mashari et al. (2003:353) suggest that “clear vision and business direction is fundamental to the success of ERP system implementation”.

According to Somers & Nelson (2001), the “ERP system implementation process consists of six phases: initiation, adoption, adaptation, acceptance, routinization, and infusion”. Companies have different approaches and reasons for implementing it.

A study by Deloitte & Touche Consulting (Computer Technology Research Corporation, 1999) categorizes organizations to drive ERP implementation into two categories: technological and operational.

The technological motivation was connected to “the year 2000 (Y2K) compliance requirements, replacement of the disparate system, improvement of quality and visibility of information, integration of business processes and systems, simplification of integration of business acquisitions into the existing technology infrastructure, replacement of older, obsolete systems, and the acquirement of the system that can support business growth” (Al-Mashari et al., 2003:360).

Operational motivation aims at “improving inadequate business performance, reducing high-cost structures, improving responsiveness to customers, simplifying ineffective, complex business processes, supporting new business strategies, expanding business globally, and standardizing business process throughout the enterprise” Al-Mashari et al (2003:353)

According to Gupta (2000:116), the key to successful implementation of ERP is as follows:

- Commitment from top management.
- Form a task force with personnel from all functional areas to foster ties between project management and business units;
- Take an assessment of hardware requirements.
- Step-by-step introduction rather than all at once.
- Start early planning on user training and support;
- Streamline decision-making so that implementation work can move quickly;

Umbre et al. (2003:245) summarize the most prominent critical success factor below:

- Clear understanding of strategic goals
- Commitment by top management
- Excellent project management
- Organizational change management
- A great implementation team
- Data Accuracy
- Extensive education and training.

For any organization to deploy ERP efficiently, the list mentioned above must be carefully followed. To determine the impact of ERP, the organization needs to understand clearly some of the points listed above at the planning, design, and implementation stages so that they can fully optimize the huge benefits of ERP.

2.5 ERP Effectiveness

Effectiveness is defined as “the extent to which an organization, by the use of certain resources, fulfills its objectives without depleting its resources and without placing undue strain on its members and society” (Mary .S. Thibodeaus, et al., 1996:23)

It is believed that effectiveness is the degree to which program or system objectives are being achieved” (Robins, 2003:34). The level to which the goals of the system are achieved or the degree to which a system can be selected to realize a set of specific mission requirements (Davenport, 2001:119).

It is believed that effectiveness evaluates the performance of business units' efforts on strategic goals and also serves as a critical component in the management planning and control process (Griffin, 1987). The researcher believes ERP effectiveness can be evaluated using a strategic model called MIT 90s critical success factor. This determines how an organization can explore IT innovation for strategic goals. It is believed that technology alone may not provide the required strategic goal without the inclusion of other critical factors.

Scott-Morton proposed MIT90's Model- a framework based on the principle that success in the IT/business alignment is about achieving synergy and balance between six key factors: Environment, Strategy, Structure, Management Process, Technology, and Individual Skills

Graphical representation of alignment sequence in MIT90s Model
Adapted from stages in information system management by Djoen, 2012

Environment: This approach describes the participation of stakeholders in the adoption of ERP in any organization. The stakeholders include suppliers, customers, and board members. There

must be an active collaboration between the external stakeholders and the staff of the organization before ERP can be effectively deployed. It is believed that the active participation of all the stakeholders will translate to effective deployment where the organization can use ERP as a strategic resource for enhanced competitive advantage.

Strategy: This describes the goals of the organization and how the organization tries to realize the goals (Djoen, 2012)

The organization's goal must be well understood and communicated to all the staff and other stakeholders before the deployment of ERP. The strategy required to realize the goal must be clearly defined before aligning the ERP system. It is evident that manual processing in mining is complex and time-consuming while ERP automation will streamline the process required to realize organization goals. A strategic fit between the business needs and the IT innovation is required.

Structure: This describes the organization structure and business process structure (Djoen, 2012). For the ERP application to be useful, the customization of the application must align with the organization and business process structure. The business process and organization structure must be communicated to the ERP vendor so that the organization can achieve a strategic fit. Misalignment of ERP may not make any impact on the production.

Management Process: “Adopting new technology requires more than purchasing hardware, management needs, to begin with the result in mind and use appropriate business processes and business strategy to construct a solution” (Lee, 2008). The top executive management team and board members play a critical role in the selection and deployment of innovative technology. The management's quest for an increase in production and efficient services could prompt the strategic implementation of ERP. It will be a difficult task in an organization where management team doesn't embrace IT innovation. The management team plays a major role making budget provision for ERP deployment and also providing required training where there are gaps. Management disposition on ERP could determine the success or failure of the system. Continual support will enhance efficient deployment.

Technology: This describes the ERP system and the hardware infrastructure that needs to be put in place for practical usage. The required hardware must function before the ERP system is

deployed. All authorized users have access to this system. This platform provides effective collaboration with all the users that leverage improved performance. Technology provides the platform for access control on the ERP deployed. Each user activity can be tracked with a different level of access control. It is evident that if the hardware infrastructure malfunctions due to power problems or hardware problems the ERP system will not function well. However, the functional hardware is requisite to effective ERP.

Individual Skills and Roles: The human resources in the organization play a crucial role in exploring the IT infrastructure to create a competitive advantage. Some staff are willing to embrace innovative technology and learn new skills required to build a leading edge with ERP. In an organization where staff have the requisite skills for ERP systems will translate to exceptional performance. Staff training should be organized in areas where skills gaps are identified for the huge benefits of ERP

The effectiveness of ERP in every organization largely depends on the capacity of the staff. Consequently, if the IT personnel are trained to provide technical support for ERP systems, they optimize the huge potential of ERP system.

2.6 Assessing ERP Effectiveness.

Assessing ERP effectiveness is a difficult task. The complexity of ERP made it difficult to develop a clear indicator to evaluate it. An organization is said to be effective if it can meet up with the set deliverables by looking at the process and structure. The different organization develops different indicators to measure the impact of innovative IT solutions. According to Gupta (2000:54), three indicators are critical to measuring the effectiveness of ERP in mining organizations which include: outcomes, processes, and structures

Outcome: This indicator focused on the deliverables of the group. For mining companies, it measures the quantity produced before and after the IT innovation. It is expected that there will be a reasonable percentage increase in production so that the increase can be measured. We can have short-term or long-term depending on what is measured. Some organization experiences a decline in production immediately after they deploy IT innovation which may later translate to an increase in production in the long run. If the deployment of ERP translates to a proportional increase in production and sales, it means the adoption is effective.

Process: According to Gupta (2000:56), “measure process effort rather than effect”. Organizational performance is measured based on the changed process. ERP adoption is expected to streamline the manual process of mining with the quick and accurate results. Effective ERP will translate to automated business process that is guided by well-informed decision. If an organization that deploys ERP did not experience streamline process, it means the system is not effective.

Structures: This indicator measure organization performance with their readiness to embrace innovate change. Some organization staff is willing to develop their capacity and adapt to change while some are resisting innovative change and this could negatively affect overall organization performance. ERP innovation is effective if the overall organization's performance improved significantly. This performance indicator could be measured for individuals and the corporate entity. These indicators require periodic review and assessment.

The researcher believes that ERP is considered useful if the organization that deployed it can meet up with her production target or deliverable in sustainable competitive advantage. It is expected that ERP will translate to a significant increase in output when compared to the generation before the advent of ERP.

2.7 Literature gaps

Most of the authors did not provide a comprehensive view of the evaluation of ERP in a mining company. This gap has prompted this study. However, many authors identified benefits and guidelines in ERP selection for manufacturing firms.

The researcher observed that some of the authors who discuss realization and evaluation did not consider the identification of benefits which is critical to the analysis.

It is believed that in the future, it might make more sense to extend the literature by including publications on inter-organizational systems that have an ERP system as their backbone (Koh et al, 2007:261). However, it might also be the case that an extended search would not add many new articles and such articles should be included in our quest for ERP.

Next to an extended literature search, future research will include cross-organizational ERP case studies to collect more accurate data insight into this field.

2.8 Conclusion.

This chapter covered a review of relevant literature so that researchers can be guided by the existing conceptual framework of ERP. The role of ERP was discussed from different authors' perspectives. The benefits of ERP were analyzed, and the implementation requirements for ERP effectiveness were stated so that the organization could be guided from the planning stage to design and implementation. A clear understanding of the organization's needs will translate to a good selection of ERP.

The author has identified some gaps in the literature reviewed so that future researchers will be guided in areas of ERP to explore.

The research methodology will be discussed in the next chapter and the justification for the choice of research methods.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

The research methodology used for this work is qualitative given its benefits and convenience. According to Easterby-Smith (2012:88), this approach aims to use language data to gain insights into social and organizational realities. The method used for collecting required information is an in-depth interview. It provides a greater diversity of views. It appears to the researcher that this method is the most suitable for data collection and analysis. According to Easterby-Smith (2012:196), “interview is often claimed to be the best method of gathering information”.

It provided an opportunity for the researcher to interact with the interviewee and have an unbiased assessment of the effectiveness of enterprise resource planning in the Dangote cement factory in Nigeria. The researcher had the opportunity to clarify some of the questions crafted to obtain the required data in evaluating the impact of ERP in the mining company.

Another research methodology that could be adopted for this study is quantitative using a questionnaire to collect data. This method provides a reliable and quick way of collecting data. “Quantitative study's great strength is providing data that is descriptive which can be analyzed with statistical tools” (Demetrius & McClain, 2012). However, this method is limited to numeric data, and it's not suitable for non-numeric data. Quantitative analytical results are limited as they provide numerical descriptions rather than detailed narratives and provide less elaborate accounts (Neil, 2006).

3.2 Case Study:

A case study is an approach in research that focuses on an in-depth study of a particular organization in a given time with an aim to provide the systematic conclusion based on analyzed data (Willig, 2008). The source data for case study includes interview, video, audio, and observations. In the case of study, the researcher actively participates in the education. The researcher carried out a study on an organization, looking at the effect of ERP in mining industry using Dangote Cement Obajana-Nigeria as a case study. It is expected that the result of the analysis will have wide acceptance in Mining Companies.

The instrumental case study was explored so that the researcher could explore the huge potentials of ERP in the mining company. The researcher crafted some questions to obtain data through a semi-structured interview. Detailed descriptive data was collected to justify the claim of the researcher on the impact of ERP in mining. The questions focused on the impact of ERP on the increase in production, sales/revenue collection, drivers of ERP implementation and some of the challenges that impede implementation. The result obtained could stimulate further research on the impact of ERP using a more holistic approach to the benefit of the process in mining.

3.3 Subject of Case Study:

The choice of Dangote Cement was inspired by the quest of the researcher to know why complex manual mining processing could be managed. The researcher worked for four years in Government established mining company where the mining process was done manually. He understands clearly the challenges that face mining company.

“Mining companies face challenges including decreasing reserves, increasing equipment complexity across facilities, rising equipment, parts and contractor costs, and declining commodity prices”(SAP, 2014:12).

Despite the challenges, he noticed that Dangote Cement increased its production line from 2 production lines to 4 within three years. The quest to know how Dangote navigates the complex supply chain in the mining industry prompted the researcher for this study.

Dangote Cement in Obajana-Nigeria is the largest Cement Plant in Africa and one of the largest in the world with an installed capacity of 12.25 million metric tons per annum. It was established in 2006 with two production lines of 5 million metric tons per annum. The third and fourth production lines were commissioned in 2014. The cement factory awarded the contract to SAP to provide ERP in 2011 so that the supply chain could be streamlined. This project was completed in 2012. One of the factors that provided a leading edge to Dangote Cement is the proximity of the company to the huge deposit of limestone which is the main raw material in cement mining. This raw material is located within the factory premises with little cost on transportation. The complex process of manual mining of limestone has been simplified with the adoption of ERP automation. Surface mining is explored because of the huge deposit of limestone in their factory site. However, there is a challenge of mining environmental pollution within the factory premises

The output of the mined limestone is taking to beneficiating plant for final processing.

The researcher noticed that Dangote Cement is the only mining company known within his environment that have deploy ERP and that can easily be accessed for study. Most of the mining companies around are yet to embrace this innovation.

Beyond the deployment of ERP in Dangote, the researcher wanted to know if the ERP installed contributed to increasing production growth and at what percentage. Consequently, the researcher desired to know the impact of ERP on strategic decision-making.

3.4 Data Sampling

This case study adopts a key informant's interview-based qualitative approach. The purpose of this method is to obtain an in-depth understanding of the impact of enterprise resource planning on mining companies. The importance of an in-depth interview is summarized by Burgess (1982:107) "The interview is the opportunity for the researcher to probe deeply to uncover new clues, open up new dimensions of problems and to secure vivid, accurate, inclusive account that is on personal experience". A sample size of four persons from different departments was selected for a one-on-one interview. The interviewee cut across Administration and Human Resources Department, Sales, and Marketing, Mines and IT department. The opportunity was given to them to provide an unbiased assessment of ERP effectiveness. Interviewees were assured of the confidentiality of the information contained which gave them the confidence to participate in the interview.

3.5 Design of Interview Schedule:

The interview questions were sub-divided into three parts namely: Company background, ERP Implementation, and ERP Evaluation Assessment.

- Company Background: It provides information about Dangote Cement looking at the year of existence, the number of staff, and the nature of business.
- ERP Implementation: Provide information about how ERP was initiated and reasons for initiating ERP. The year ERP was implemented, drivers for the decision to adopt ERP,

Consequently, information about ERP's contribution to production was sought. The percentage increase in production due to ERP adoption was also asked amidst other questions.

□ Evaluation Assessment: The impacts of ERP was evaluated with some indicators like organization sales/profit, business process improvement, and customer satisfaction. The challenges of ERP were captured.

It is believed that the semi-structured interview questions provided an unbiased assessment of the impact of ERP in Dangote Cement.

3.6 Data Analysis

The qualitative approach used is grounded analysis. This approach made provision for data to speak for itself, it allows a process for intuition for a deeper understanding of the data Easterby-Smith (2012:89). It is evident to the researcher that this approach is robust and holistic to make a deduction from analyzed data. Grounded analysis offers a more open approach to data analysis and the source data can be text produced from empirical research (interview data) or external text which might take the form of reports Easterby-Smith (2012:88).

Researcher believed that grounded analysis requires staying close to the data that is analyzed. The data obtained is systematically analyzed to bring out themes that can be further scrutinized before concluding.

Another approach that would have been suitable is content analysis. In this approach, the researcher interrogates the data for constructs and ideas that have been decided in advance (Easterby-Smith, 2012:88).

This approach is not preferred because it is not robust and holistic like grounded analysis.

NVivo software was used to analyze the data (interview) given the under-listed benefits of using the software for qualitative data as presented by Dr. Ana Garcia in “NVivo Basics Getting Started” available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Xe0NpJPLQ6k>.

Benefits of Nvivo Software.

It allows for classifying, sorting, and arranging many types of non-numerical data such as field notes, video, audio, excel, etc.

It helps to examine the relationship with data.

It provides an organized storage file system that can quickly be searched and located.

It helps to analyze data to determine the relationship that exists between the data obtained.

It helps to visualize projects and draw models/charts.

3.7 Reliability and Validity

Reliability is defined as the level to which results are consistent over time and are an accurate reflection of the total population of the study (Joppe, 2000). From the research work carried out, the sample size of four persons cut across four departments the ERP has been deployed and functional. The staff selected cut across top executive management staff, mid-manager, and junior staff. The aggregate of four persons from different grade levels and departments will provide an unbiased assessment. Consequently, the visit to each interviewee was scheduled on different dates, and it clearly stated that the information obtained was strictly for academic work. The questions selected focused on the effectiveness

Validity determines whether the research truly measures that which it intended to measure and how truthful the research results are (Winter, 2000). The statement of problems that were identified had been proffered with solutions which are the objective of the study carried out. The in-depth interview conducted provided an opportunity to obtain to explain their perception on the effectiveness of ERP in Dangote Cement Company. Reasons were given to issues like increase in production, sales and revenue generation, and organization performance.

The NVivo software that was used to analyze the data is reliable software that provides an accurate result that can be trusted.

3.8 Ethical Concerns and Safeguards.

The ethical issue was given due consideration in this research. To gain access to Dangote Cement, a telephone call was put across to the General Manager Administration/Head of Human Resources who scheduled a meeting in his office. An Official letter from the school requesting for approval to carry out a research work was officially submitted and approved because the integrity of the institution that wrote the letter and the relevance of the research project. Participant Consent Form was presented as a supporting document which shows a brief description of the research and what participation involves.

Each participant was assured of listed ethical concerns & safeguards;

- Ensuring the confidentiality of research data.
- Protecting the anonymity of individuals or organizations.
- Avoiding deception about the nature or aims of the research.
- Respecting the dignity of research participants.
- Ensuring a fully informed consent of research participants.
- Protecting the privacy of research subjects

The Management of the organization approved each interviewee to participate after all the required documentation has been done. The participants were convinced that the required information from the researcher was purely for academic exercise. They were obliged to provide an unbiased perception of the advent of ERP in their organization. Each of the participants accented to take part in the research by appending their name and signature on the participant consent form.

3.7 Conclusion.

This chapter shows the research method used for this study. Qualitative data analysis was used. An in-depth interview was used as an instrument to collect data from four persons who were cut across different departments.

The choice of the case study was justified following the relevance of the topic to the mining industry. It was clearly stated that Dangote Cement in Nigeria was chosen following the fact that it's the largest Cement factory in Nigeria and the only mining company that had deployed ERP which the researcher can easily access for a study.

The data obtained was analyzed using grounded theory with the help of NVivo software. This software helps to examine the relationship with data. It allows classifying, sorting, and arranging many types of non-numerical data such as field notes, video, audio, excel.

The reliability and validity of the study were discussed. It is evident from the result obtained that the participants provided an unbiased perception about the impact of ERP in their company. It is believed that the four persons that were interviewed are a true reflection of the total population of the company.

The rigor the researcher went through to obtain the result and the robust software used to analyze made the researcher believe that the study can be trusted with wide acceptance in the mining industry.

Ethical concerns and safeguard issues were strictly adhered to. The participants were assured of their anonymity and the confidentiality of the research data.

The next chapter discussed the analysis and interpretation to validate the perception of the author on the impact of ERP in mining sector.

Chapter 4

Analysis and Interpretation

The researcher selected four persons to participate in the interview from the Admin & Human Resources Department, Information Technology Department, Sales & Marketing Department, and Mines Department. It is believed that these interviewees from different departments and grade levels will provide unbiased assessments of different perspectives of ERP in their company.

4.1 Qualitative Data Analysis & Interpretation

The data obtained from the interviewee were analyzed using some indicators that were captured in the interview questionnaire. These helped to analyze some of the research questions generated to determine the effectiveness of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) in the Mining Industry. Some of the pertinent questions used are shown below.

Who initiated ERP in their company?

The participants gave varying responses on how ERP was initiated and deployed. Some of the participants said the top management executive initiated this innovative decision while some people believed that the chief executive officer influenced the decision. It is obvious from their responses that there was an acceptance at the top management level for this innovation to be implemented. The reason for this adoption was shared by the two management staff that took part in the interview: They said they wanted to provide real-time information that will enhance customer satisfaction and also increase their production. The quest to streamline their process was also identified as one of the drivers that propelled them for the adoption of this innovation.

Which areas of ERP functions were implemented? It was clear to the researcher from the interviewee's response that the ERP installed cut across the Mines Department, Survey, Admin & Human Resource, Finance, Sales and Marketing, IT, and Business Intelligence. It was made known to the researcher that before the advent of ERP, each department had a stand-alone software that tracks their activities within the department.

Did ERP implementation increase long-term production? If yes, by what percentage?

Three out of the four participants agree that there was an increase in production of varying percentage. One of the participants said he doesn't know the percentage increase, but he knew there was an increase. The increase in production attributed to the ERP adoption given the fact the complex mining process was streamline. Another person said the increase was because ERP deployed was able to create an avenue to interact with their customers at this moment increasing their market share compared to other competitors that don't have such IT platform. Customers' satisfaction has been enhanced with the IT innovation. The percentage increase in production ranges from 35% to 65%.

The adoption of ERP has given Dangote Cement a competitive edge. Other cement mining companies still use manual processing.

Switching to ERP, an immediate short-term decline in organizational performance was noticed? If yes, by what percentage?

It was observed that the advent of ERP brought about a decline in organizational performance within the first six months. Another participant said there was a decline in performance within the first eight months. The other two participants said the decline in organization performance was noticed within the first three months. The percentage decline ranges from 20% to 32%

The reason for the decline was obvious in the participant's response. The top management team that initiated the ERP adoption did not communicate clearly to the casual staff and junior staff that worked in the mines and survey department. It was difficult for some of the staff to embrace this innovation because it was strange to them. In another opinion, the first batch of people that were trained was the top management and mid-management level. This demoralized some of the junior staff for not allowed being trained early. It took the organization almost ten months to sensitize and train staff. Another reason was that the ERP did not work well within the first three months. It could be an integration challenge that affected the organization's performance within this period.

Does the adoption of ERP lead to an increase in sales/revenue generation?

Some of the participants believed that there had been a marginal increase in sales/revenue generation. Others believed that the profit realized within the last two years when compared to

the huge cost of installation is small. However, the adoption of ERP has brought about the increase in sales which range from 21% to 35%.

It is believed that the major reason why the profit increase is that they were able to expand their market share and collaborate with their customers

Some of the indicators analyzed with NVivo are shown below.

The four respondents agree that ERP deployment increases production by different percentages as shown below. However, one of the respondents said he didn't know the percentage increase in cement production.

Increase in Cement Production

[<Internals\Interview\Hassan>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.14% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.14% Coverage

Increased Production	High
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[<Internals\Interview\Ibrahim>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.14% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.14% Coverage

Increased Production	High
----------------------	------

[<Internals\Interview\Ofurum>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.13% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.13% Coverage

Increased Production	High
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[<Internals\Interview\Stella>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.18% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.18% Coverage

Increased Production	low
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Percentage increase in production.

[<Internals\Interview\Hassan>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.10% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.10% Coverage

65%

[<Internals\Interview\Ibrahim>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.41% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.41% Coverage

I don't know

[<Internals\Interview\Ofurum>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.10% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.10% Coverage

35%

[<Internals\Interview\Stella>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.09% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.09% Coverage

44%

Quality of Information Generated from ERP

The interviewees agree that the quality of information generated has been enhanced with ERP deployment.

[<Internals\Interview\Hassan>](#) - § 2 references coded [0.27% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.14% Coverage

Integrated and better-quality of information	High
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[<Internals\Interview\Ibrahim>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.14% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.14% Coverage

Integrated and better-quality of information	High
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[<Internals\Interview\Ofurum>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.13% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.13% Coverage

Integrated and better quality of information	High
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[<Internals\Interview\Stella>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.12% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.12% Coverage

Integrated and better-quality of information	High
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Sales Profit/Increase in Revenue Generation.

Each Interviewee had a different perception of the sales profit. Some believed that profit compared to cost of production has increased marginally while some believe that the increase in sales compared to cost of production is low.

[<Internals\Interview\Hassan>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.14% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.14% Coverage

Increase in Profit	High
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[<Internals\Interview\Ibrahim>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.14% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.14% Coverage

Increase in Profit	High
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[<Internals\Interview\Ofurum>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.13% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.13% Coverage

Increase in Profit	High
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[<Internals\Interview\Stella>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.09% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.09% Coverage

Increase in Profit	Low
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Huge cost of deployment.

The huge cost of deployment has been identified as the most challenging factor militating against ERP deployment in the mining industry. Interviewee responses are shown below.

Cost of ERP Deployment

[<Internals\Interview\Hassan>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.30% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.30% Coverage

Huge Cost of ERP deployment	Very high
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[<Internals\Interview\Ibrahim>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.31% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.31% Coverage

Huge Cost of ERP Deployment	Very high
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[<Internals\Interview\Ofurum>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.17% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.17% Coverage

Huge Cost of ERP Deployment	High
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[<Internals\Interview\Stella>](#) - § 1 reference coded [0.27% Coverage]

Reference 1 - 0.27% Coverage

Huge Cost of ERP deployment	Very high
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Taking a critical look at ERP deployment in Dangote Cement Factory, it's obvious that there has been a notable increase in cement production since the advent of ERP in 2012.

According to the research, the top management team of the company embraced the deployment of ERP to respond to environmental challenges. The pace of technological progress and change has become so fierce in recent years that organization needs to respond quickly to new environmental challenges and the need to continuously renew their technological capacity, particularly in information technology to ensure their prosperity and sustainability (Gera & Gu, 2004:42).

The four respondents agree that the advent of ERP has increased production marginally. The increase in production from the respondents ranges from 65% to 35%. It is believed that firms that combine ICT with organizational change have a high incidence of productivity improvement and a high rate of innovation (Gera & Gu, 2004:43).

Consequently, the researcher strongly believes that the organizational culture in Dangote Cement encourages innovation which has translated to increase in organization performance. "The organization culture may be a contributing factor in the extent to which creativity and innovation occur in an organization" (Johnson, 2010: 11).

It is evident from the research carried out that the quality of information obtained has been enhanced. The entire respondent said the quality of information obtained with ERP was high. Management teams are well-informed, and their decisions are guided to enhance strategic advantage. Consequently, processes are handled on a single platform; decision makers get a single, unified view of key performance indicators (SAP, 2014:11).

The greatest challenge that militates against ERP deployment as identified by the interviewee is the huge cost required to deploy it. The business chain in Mining Industry is very complex, and it requires a huge capital to deploy.

4.2 Conclusion:

This chapter discussed the qualitative data analyzed using NVivo Software. Some of the critical indicators that were relevant to the effectiveness of the enterprise resource planning system were evaluated. The increase in production and the reasons for the increase were analyzed. Each

participant expresses his perception of the adoption of ERP and its impact on production. The drivers for the adoption of ERP were discussed. It is evident from the participants that the top management team of the company initiated the adoption of ERP. However, this innovative concept was not communicated to other staff which caused a decline in performance within the first six months. It is believed that the sales/revenue of the company has increased.

The huge cost of deployment was identified as the greatest challenge of ERP deployment in this company. A huge capital was invested in ERP deployment in 2012 by SAP company Germany.

The next chapter discussed the summary of major findings, gaps in the study, and areas of future research.

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Summary of Major Findings.

This study is concerned with evaluating the effectiveness of enterprise resource planning in the mining industry using Dangote Cement factory-Obajana in Nigeria as a case study. It is the largest cement factory in Africa and one of the largest in the world with an average production capacity of 12.5 million metric tons per year. The cement factory was established in 2006. The choice of this organization was because it is the only mining company that is accessible to the author that has automated their mining activities with ERP. However, ERP was deployed in 2012 to provide a leading edge for a cement factory in Africa.

Most of the previous studies on enterprise resource planning in the mining industry focused on the integration and significance of ERP implementation in mining (Manouchehr, 2008:34).

However, few studies devote sufficient attention to ERP users' perceived benefits.

This research work focused on the effectiveness of ERP in the Mining Industry. It is evident in this study that the adoption of ERP was influenced by the top management team given their quest for a competitive edge in Africa. "Top managers have a crucial role in creating and providing conditions needed for project success" (Staehr, 2010:78). It is believed that the relative impact recorded in production is because the top management team embraced this innovation. However, it was observed that the adoption of ERP caused a decline in performance within the first six months after deployment because other staff were not sensitized before the adoption of the system. The top management team did not communicate clearly to other stakeholders before the advent of ERP.

Other critical indicators like an increase in production increase in sales profit, improved the quality of information generated to guide management decisions. Consequently, challenges that militate against the effective implementation of ERP were identified. The reasons for the response of each participant on the indicators identified were discussed to provide depth to some of the issues that contributed to the impact of ERP.

A qualitative research method was adopted using the semi-structured in-depth interview to collect data from four staff in different departments cutting across top management, mid-management, and junior staff. Their responses were analyzed using NVivo software. The adoption of ERP has increased cement production and also improved sales profit.

The findings of the researcher support the view of many authors that huge benefits could be explored from ERP implementation if the organization culture embraced this innovation as evident in Dangote Cement. “Corporations may enthusiastically engage in ERP implementation, as long as perceived benefits exceed perceived risks and costs” Esteves, (2009:26).

According to Wei-Wen,(2011:43), some studies have discussed significant factors for ERP implementation challenges, as well as listed various benefits that may result from implementing ERP systems

5.2 Managerial Implications

For mining companies to thrive and have a competitive edge, they need to manage and optimize an increasingly complex supply chain. Leading Mining companies with superlative performance know that operational excellence is key to operational challenges (SAP, 2014:19).

Implementing new software solutions is a strategic undertaking that requires a commitment from top management staff as well as contributions from other staff as evident in Dangote Cement Factory. Their huge investment in SAP enterprise resource planning has yielded a result within the last three years. However, the researcher believes that organizations can fully optimize ERP systems by training more staff on their usage. More indigenous engineers need to be trained to provide technical support when the need arises without inviting the service provider from Germany.

Powerful analytical tools from SAP help mining companies identify trends and patterns in areas such as operations and profitability, which can improve business decisions (SAP, 2014:21). It is evident from the research carried out that ERP was successfully deployed in Dangote Cement looking at their business process that has been streamlined and their production that has been increased.

5.3 Suggestions for Management in Other Mining Companies.

Organizational values and beliefs must be well understood and communicated. Users' resistance to change may hinder deployment. Users who are not receptive to innovative change may not embrace strategic IT/business alignment

“Culture plays an increasingly important role in information system initiatives and receives considerable attention from researchers who have studied the variety of aspects of its role in information system initiatives” (Walsham, 2002:69). Organizational culture is critical to the successful implementation of the innovative project.

Sensitization is required for board members and top managers who are not literate on ERP implementation. They need to see the huge potential benefits of ERP implementation in Mining that can enhance competitive advantage. Sensitization will create awareness and the need for sustainable competitive advantage. Highly aligned organizations do indeed leverage more matured governance practices compared to poorly aligned organizations (De Haes & Van Grembergen, 2009:123).

Capacity Development of the Project Management Team:

Smaller projects are easier to implement and control, but to replicate into larger organizations requires having the right skill set in the project team composition (Partho, 2013:55). Relevant training should be provided for staff before and after deployment of ERP in areas where skills gaps are identified.

The right skill in the right composition is key to project success (Partho, 2013:55)

IT governance; “IT governance consists of the leadership and organization structures and processes that ensure that the organization IT sustains and extend the organization strategy and objectives” (ITGI, 2003:44; Van Grembergen, 2001:83). IT governance should be institutionalized to proffer solutions to the perceived obstacles.

IT governance will provide a relational mechanism for active participation and collaborative relationships among, corporative executives, IT management, and business management (Peterson, 2003:112). Effective collaboration will break cultural barriers that could hinder

strategic information system planning implementation. A good interpersonal relationship will foster the participation of all users

Outsource to a reputable firm; looking at the complexity of ERP implementation, mining organizations must outsource ERP deployment to a reputable firm with a track record of successful completion of similar projects. Customization will not be difficult for a reputable firm to handle. Training should be provided for users so that they can optimize IT capabilities for business value

5.4 Limitation & Area of Future Research.

There are some limitations concerning the sample and the data used for evaluation.

Our sample includes a large mining company (Dangote Cement Factory). Future research could use smaller mining companies to evaluate the effectiveness of ERP. Consequently, an effort should be made in the future to use a mining company that has not deployed ERP as a control organization with another mining company that has deployed ERP. This will provide a better comparison model to evaluate effectiveness. My study was limited to the interview conducted. However, a better result would have been obtained if I had requested for secondary sources of information like production reports before the advent of ERP and reports after the deployment. This would have provided robust data for analysis.

For future research, there is an increasing need to deepen analyses of ERP users' perceived benefits, using organizations that have implemented ERP to gain meaningful findings. Unfortunately, the previous literature has contented itself with listing a miscellaneous set of ERP benefits that do not necessarily share the same importance.

5.5 Conclusion:

To achieve superior performance, an Information Technology/Information Systems (IT/IS) plan requires effective leadership, a culture that is receptive to change, and adaptable systems that are all aligned with business strategy” (Khani, 2011:82).

This chapter discussed some of the major findings in this study regarding the effectiveness of ERP in Dangote Cement. Suggestions were discussed for other mining companies to learn so that they can have effective deployment and usage for the huge benefits to be explored.

Limitations and areas of future research were discussed so that people can be guided to have a robust study that will have wide relevance and acceptance.

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ETHICS RESPONSE FORM

Researcher name (student): Ayo Oludare	Faculty reviewer: Dr. Dimitrios	Date of Review:
Working Title of Proposal or summary of study scope: Effectiveness of Enterprise Resource Planning System in Mining Company		
Proposal attached? ___ Yes ___ No	Academic Honesty Declaration signed? ___ Yes ___ No	

Each of the ethical standards below must be adequately addressed by the researcher in order to obtain ethics approval.

In the first column, the RESEARCHER (student) should perform a self-check using these 35 questions before submitting the ethics form to the faculty member supervising the study. In each row of the first column, the RESEARCHER should enter YES, NO, or NA as well as a very brief explanation. The Academic Honesty Declaration must be attached and should be signed and dated.

In the second column the ETHICS REVIEWER (supervising faculty member) will enter YES, NO, or NA to confirm or challenge the RESEARCHER'S self-check on each standard. With each NO, the ETHICS REVIEWER will indicate what revisions are required for ethics approval. The faculty reviewer will also render a decision at the end of this form and return the form to the RESEARCHER.

If the ETHICS REVIEWER (supervising faculty member) is able to approve "as is" then the third column is left blank.

In the third column, the **RESEARCHER (student)** will respond to each of the ETHICS REVIEWER’S concerns to explain where/how each of the reviewer’s concerns was met in the resubmitted materials.

	Researcher’s ethics self-check In each row, the researcher should confirm compliance with the ethical standard by entering “Yes,” “No,” or “N/A,” along with a brief defense of the response (i.e., stating keywords that point to how the ethical standard has been met).	Ethics Reviewer’s assessment: After the researcher has presented the evidence for compliance with each ethical standard, the Ethics Reviewer should either confirm by entering “Yes” or challenge with “No.” With each “No,” the reviewer must specify what revisions are needed to obtain ethics approval.	Researcher’s response to Ethics Reviewer Researcher must use this column to <u>explain how and where</u> each of the Ethics Reviewer’s concerns (in the second column) has been addressed.
<i>Example: Will data be stored securely?</i>	<i>Yes. Data files will be kept on a password protected computer.</i>	<i>No. Please also address how the paper surveys will be secured prior to being entered as electronic files.</i>	<i>Paper surveys will be in a locked file cabinet. Proposal has been updated.</i>
<p>The first 11 questions apply to all studies (even when the researcher is not interacting with participants to collect new data). Hover the mouse over the footnoted words to view extra tips and definitions.</p>			
1. Are participant recruitment and data collection steps ⁱ adequately described,	Yes. Participants’ recruitment strategy has been planned. Four		

such that the study's risks and burdens can be discerned?	staff from each department will be contacted for participation.		
2. Will the research procedures ensure privacy ⁱⁱ during data collection?	Yes. Data collection instruments and other relevant documents will be kept secured immediately after collection in my locked cupboard. The softcopy will be kept with password.		
3. Will data be stored securely ⁱⁱⁱ with adequate provisions to maintain the confidentiality of the data?	Yes. Softcopy will be stored on my laptop with password and no copy will be kept in my external hard disk or mobile storage device. Hardcopy will be kept in my locked cupboard to prevent unauthorized access.		
4. Will the data be stored for at least 5 years?	No. Stored data will be kept for less than five years.		
5. If participants' names or contact info will be recorded in the research records, are they absolutely necessary ^{iv} ?	No, participant names or contact info will not be recorded. My interest is in the data collected and not their identity.		
6. Do the research procedures and analysis/write-up plans include all possible measures to ensure that participant identities are not directly or indirectly ^v disclosed? For secondary data analyses, the proposal must clearly state	Yes. My procedure and analysis will only depicts sample data collected and not participant identity. For secondary data proprietary information from the organization will not be captured		

when/how de-identification will occur.			
7. Have all potential psychological^{vi} , relationship^{vii} , legal^{viii} , economic/professional^{ix} , physical^x , and other risks been fully acknowledged^{xi} and described?	No. Not all risk has been described. Details of the potential risk will be compiled after my discussion with the CEO of the mining company		
8. Have the above risks been minimized ^{xii} as much as possible?	Yes. To have credible result, the anticipated risk will be minimized.		
9. Has the researcher proactively managed any potential conflicts of interest^{xiii} ? Note that student researchers may <u>not</u> utilise research assistants to recruit participants or collect research data on behalf of the researcher.	No. I don't have dual role with the context of my research. The case study is mining company and it is not my place of work		
10. Are the research risks and burdens^{xiv} reasonable, in consideration of the new knowledge^{xv} that this research design can offer?	Yes. Research risk is worthwhile looking at the potential benefits of ERP in Mining Company. The research work will avail me opportunity to learn innovative strategy to mining production in Nigeria		
11. Is the research site willing to provide an Authorisation Letter (or email) granting permission^{xvi} for all relevant data^{xvii} access, access to participants, facility use, and/or use of personnel time for research purposes?	NA. I have not informed them officially on my interest to collect data.		

The remaining questions only apply to studies that involve recruiting participants to collect new data (such as surveys, interviews, observations).

____ Please place an X on this line if **NONE** of the questions in the next section are applicable to the proposed study.

<p>12. Applicable for student researchers: Will this researcher be appropriately qualified^{xviii} and supervised^{xix} in all data collection procedures?</p>	<p>Yes. Am qualified for data collection procedure following the skills I have learned in Research Method. Approved Supervisor will guide me when necessary</p>		
<p>13. Is participant recruitment coordinated in a manner that is non-coercive^{xx}? Coercive elements include: leveraging an existing relationship to “encourage” participation, recruiting in a group^{xxi} setting, extravagant compensation, recruiting individuals in a context of their treatment or evaluation^{xxii}, etc. A researcher must disclose here whether/how the researcher may already be known to the participants and explain how perceptions of coerced research participation will be minimized^{xxiii}.</p>	<p>NA. The target group will be contacted via email after getting approval from the CEO. There will be no group setting where participants will be brought together to express their view on sample data to avoid bias information.</p>		
<p>14. If anyone would be excluded from participating, is their exclusion justified? Is their exclusion handled respectfully and without stigma^{xxiv}?</p>	<p>Yes. My interest in the study to have willing people who are ready to provide correct information. There will be no stigma</p>		

<p>15. Where the researcher proposes to use an interpreter, has adequate consideration been given to the interpreter's training regarding confidentiality and principles of informed consent, etc.?</p>	<p>NA. Interpreter is not required in my mail questionnaire. The target group understands basic English Language.</p>		
<p>16. Do the informed consent^{xxv} procedures provide adequate time to review the study information and ask questions before giving consent?</p>	<p>Yes. There is stipulated time to review and ask questions</p>		
<p>17. Will informed consent be appropriately^{xxvi} documented?</p>	<p>Yes. Informed consent will be securely kept in my laptop with password on it.</p>		
<p>18. Is the participant information sheet (PIS) written using language that will be understandable^{xxvii} to the potential participants?</p>	<p>Yes. PIS is written in English. Participants understand basic English Language.</p>		
<p>19. Does the PIS include an understandable^{xxviii} explanation of the research purpose?</p>	<p>Yes. PIS contained detailed information which is simple to read and understand.</p>		
<p>20. Does the PIS explain the sample's inclusion criteria in such a way^{xxix} that the participants can understand how/why THEY are being asked to participate?</p>	<p>Yes. PIS will contain detail inclusion criteria so that participant will be obliged to provide correct information/</p>		
<p>21. Does the PIS clearly state that participation is voluntary?</p>	<p>Yes. PIS contained clear information that participation is</p>		

	voluntary.		
22. Does the PIS convey that the participant has the right^{xxx} to decline or discontinue participation at any time?	Yes. PIS will clearly state that participant has right to decline at any point in time.		
23. Does the PIS include an understandable description of the data collection procedures?	Yes. Detail description of data collection procedure will be clearly stated.		
24. Does the PIS include an estimate of the time commitment^{xxxi} for participation?	Yes. Estimated time will be clearly stated		
25. Does the PIS describe any thank you gifts, compensation, or reimbursement to participants (for travel costs, etc.) or lack thereof?	No. Incentive in monetary value will not be included in the PIS. Traveling cost is not required in my mail questionnaire but will make provision for money to post the questionnaire to me which will not reflect in the PIS		
26. Does the PIS include a description of reasonably foreseeable risks^{xxxii} or discomforts?	No. Anticipated risk will not be included in the PIS		
27. Does the PIS include a description of anticipated benefits to participants^{xxxiii} and/or others?	Yes. The benefits of research work to the mining company will be stated.		
28. Does the PIS explain how the participant can contact the researcher and the university's Research Participant Advocate? (USA number 001-612-312-	Yes. Email address and mobile contact of the researcher and School Contacts will be clearly stated		

1210 or email address Ethics@roehampton-online.com)			
29. Does the PIS describe how privacy will be maintained ^{xxxiv} ?	Yes. It will be clearly stated the research will only serve intended purpose. Confidentiality will be assured to the participants.		
30. Does the PIS disclose all potential conflicts of interest (specifying that this study is separate from the researcher's other professional role)?	NA. No conflict of interest since the research will only serve intended purpose		
31. Do the consent documents preserve the participant's legal ^{xxxv} rights?	Yes. Participant legal right will not be violated.		
<p>The remaining questions regarding sensitive content and vulnerable populations should be reviewed and addressed by the researcher (student) and faculty reviewer, but must also be confirmed by the International Online Research Ethics Committee before the study may go ahead.</p> <p><u> X </u> Please place an X on this line if <u> NONE </u> of the questions in the next section are applicable to the proposed study.</p>			
32. If vulnerable ^{xxxvi} individuals will be specifically sought out as participants, is such targeted recruitment justified ^{xxxvii} by a research design that will specifically benefit that vulnerable group at large?			
33. If the researcher happens to also serve in a trusted or authoritative ^{xxxviii} role			

<p>to the participant (e.g., health care provider, teacher etc.), do the recruitment procedures ensure voluntary participation?</p>			
<p>34. If the research procedures might reveal or create an acute psychological state that necessitates referral, are there suitable procedures in place to manage this?</p>			
<p>35. If the research procedures might reveal criminal activity, child/elder abuse, or employer policy non-compliance that necessitates^{xxxix} reporting, are there suitable procedures in place for managing this? Are limits to confidentiality (i.e., duty to report) appropriately mentioned in the Participant Information Sheet?</p>			

ETHICS APPROVAL DECISION

THIS DOCUMENT MUST BE POSTED IN THE GRADEBOOK AFTER THE SUPERVISING FACULTY MEMBER HAS RENDERED A DECISION.

The supervising Faculty Member will mark an X next to box A, B, or C. If box A or B is marked, then the supervising faculty member will also mark an X next to the applicable subcategory (1, 2, 3, etc.):

A. APPROVED VIA EXPEDITED (LIGHT TOUCH) ETHICS REVIEW:

- As the supervising faculty member, I confirm that all applicable criteria 1-35 above are met with either a “Yes” or “N/A.”
- I understand my responsibilities as supervisor, and will ensure to the best of my abilities that the student investigator abides by the University’s policy on Research Ethics at all times.
- I affirm that the research activities fall entirely within the parameters of the design indicated with an X below (1,2 or 3) that the International Online Research Ethics Committee has authorized faculty members to approve via the expedited (light touch) review:

1. analysis of public documents, artifacts, behaviour or data;

2. secondary analysis of existing data that is privately held but released for research purposes (with all identifiers removed);

3. surveys or interviews of non-vulnerable adults on non-sensitive topics (i.e., no potential to participants of coercion, distress, loss of work/school time, damage to professional reputation). Vulnerable populations include children, clinic patients, prisoners, military personnel, facility residents, anyone over whom the researcher holds authority (e.g., students, subordinates), anyone who might feel undue pressure to participate in the study, and any individuals with severe enough mental disabilities to interfere with capacity to consent to the study.

B. REFERRED TO ETHICS COMMITTEE:

- As the supervising faculty member, I am referring this study to the full ethics committee (IOREC) because [mark 1, 2, 3, 4 or Other below].
- I will email the student's ethics application and all attachments as a single zip file to the ethics committee via Ethics@roehampton-online.com, copying the Programme Director.

The ethics committee accepts applications until 5 pm GMT on the 3rd Thursday of every month.

Decisions and feedback will be emailed to the student and DA within 5 business days after the 4th Thursday of the month.

		1. the researcher proposes to collect data from vulnerable individuals such as children, clinic patients, prisoners, military personnel, facility residents, anyone over whom the researcher holds authority (e.g., students, subordinates), anyone who might feel undue pressure to participate in the study, and any individuals with severe enough mental disabilities to interfere with capacity to consent to the study.
		2. some (potential) participants may find the research topic or premise sensitive
		3. participants' jobs or livelihoods may be placed at any risk by the study activities
		4. the participants' culture and/or international location suggest that extra participant protections may be necessary
		Other: _____
	<p>C. REVISIONS REQUIRED:</p> <p>The student needs to revise the proposal and ethics materials to address the concerns in the second column and resubmit to me before I can select A or B above.</p>	

Footnotes

ⁱ In order to weigh potential risks against benefits, the researcher first needs to plan and clearly articulate all of the following that apply:
how existing data or contact information of potential participants will be obtained,
format and context of the initial contact with potential participants,
informed consent procedures,
assignment to groups (if applicable),
description of any pilot activities,
data collection steps,
transcript review and/or membercheck (if applicable), and
how results will be shared with stakeholders.

ⁱⁱ Privacy risks might include unintended breach of confidential information (such as educational or medical records); being observed/overheard by others while meeting researcher or providing data; or intrusion on the privacy of others who are not involved in the study (e.g. participant's family).

ⁱⁱⁱ Secure data storage requires password protection on electronic files and locks for physical data.

^{iv} Note that consent forms do not require signatures if the participant can indicate consent by some action such as clicking on a link, returning a completed survey, etc.

^v Participant identities might be "indirectly" and unintentionally disclosed if a researcher's final research report fails to withhold demographic details or site descriptions that might permit a reader to deduce the identity of a participant. So the researcher needs to think about which demographic descriptors are most important to collect and report, while ensuring that the identity of individual participants is protected. Also, the name of the site/organization is typically masked in scholarly research though in some cases, the organization can elect to publicize their name along with the research results.

^{vi} Psychological risks include stress greater than what one would experience in daily life (e.g., materials or topics that could be considered sensitive, offensive, threatening, degrading).

^{vii} Relationship risks are present if the recruitment or data collection process are likely to alter the existing dynamics between the researcher and participant (who may be coworkers or have some professional relationship), among participants (if they know one another), or between the participant and the participant's friends, coworkers, or family members.

^{viii} Legal risks are present if data collection might result in a participant's disclosure of violation of laws.

^{ix} Economic/professional risks are present if data collection could result in the participant disclosing violation of workplace policies, disagreement with leadership decisions, poor work performance, or anything else that could be damaging to the participant's position, professional reputation, promotability, or employability. Risks are acceptable but participants need to be made aware of professional risks during the consent process so they can make an informed decision.

^x Physical risks are not common in social science research but would involve risk of serious physical injury to the participant or the researcher.

^{xi} Minimal risks are acceptable but must be identified upfront. Minimal risk is defined as when: "the probability and magnitude of harm or discomfort anticipated in the research are not greater in and of themselves than those ordinarily encountered in daily life."

^{xii} The researcher is responsible for planning measures that will provide participants with reasonable protection from privacy loss, distress, psychological harm, economic loss, damage to professional reputation, and other possible harms.

^{xiii} A conflict of interest is caused when the researcher has some sort of dual role in the research context, such as being a teacher, therapist, investor, business-owner, manager, etc.

Conflict of interest must be managed to ensure that the research reveals "truth," not just the outcome that the researcher might desire to see due to their other role.

^{xiv} All research activities place some degree of burden on the participants by asking the participants to share personal information, volunteer time, and assume risks.

^{xv} Examples of "new knowledge" include: effectively addressing a gap in the literature, generating new theory, enhancing understanding of a phenomenon, assessing effectiveness of a particular professional practice, addressing a local practical problem via data analysis.

^{xvi} No documentation of permission is required (a) if the researcher will simply be asking organizations to distribute research invitations on the researcher's behalf, or (b) if the researcher is using only public means to identify/contact participants.

^{xvii} Note that when medical, educational, or business records would be analyzed or used to identify potential research participants, the site needs to explicitly approve access to data for research purposes (even if the researcher normally has access to that data to perform his or her job).

^{xviii} Researchers must be able to document their training in the data collection techniques and the ethics committee might require the researcher to obtain additional training prior to ethics approval. For most student researchers, the research course sequence is sufficient but some research procedures (such as interviewing people with mental disabilities) may require additional training. For psychological assessments, the manual indicates specific qualifications required. Data collection from children requires a background check/clearance through a local agency.

^{xix} Remote supervision is suitable for most studies but onsite supervision may be required for certain types of sensitive data collection (e.g., interviews or assessment regarding emotional topics).

^{xx} For example, anonymous surveys and/or low-pressure communications such as email invitations permit potential participants to opt out with minimal fear of retaliation or other negative consequences.

^{xxi} It is not ethically acceptable to invite a “captive audience” to participate in research on the spot (i.e., to ask an entire class or a group of meeting attendees to complete a survey during their session). Such a dynamic would not provide sufficient privacy or respect for their right to decline research participation. However, a researcher may use the last few minutes of a meeting to introduce a study and distribute materials, such that the potential participants can then take their time to decide later about participation.

^{xxii} Generally, data collection cannot be approved during work hours or school hours unless a “free period” has been identified (e.g., lunch) so the research activities can be separated from the participants’ regular activities. It is important to maintain an “opt in” dynamic rather than implying that employees/students/group members are expected to participate.

^{xxiii} Completion of the study directly benefits the student (allowing him or her to obtain a degree), and so the researcher should minimize the potential for either (a) conflict of interest or (b) perceived coercion to participate. Researchers who are in positions of authority or familiarity must take extra precautions to ensure that potential participants are not pressured to take part in their study. Examples: an instructor researcher may recruit her students AFTER grades have been assigned; a psychologist researcher may recruit clients from ANOTHER psychologist’s practice; a manager researcher may conduct ANONYMOUS data collection so that subordinates do not perceive their responses or [non]participation as being associated with their job standing.

^{xxiv} When applicable, the exclusion criteria should be listed on the recruitment material (flyer, invitation email, etc.) or participant information sheet (PIS) to prevent situations in which the researcher rejects volunteers in a stigmatizing manner.

^{xxv} Informed consent is not just a form; it is a process of explaining the study to the participant and encouraging questions before the participant makes a decision about participation.

^{xxvi} While documenting consent via signature is common, note that anonymous surveys can obtain “implied consent” by informing the participant, “To protect your privacy, no consent signature is requested. Instead, you may indicate your consent by clicking here/returning this survey in the enclosed envelope.” It is also acceptable to audiorecord verbal consent for interviews, in order to not have any record of the interviewee’s name.

^{xxvii} The ethics committee encourages tailoring the language to the readers as long as a professional tone is maintained.

^{xxviii} Minimal jargon should be used during the informed consent process. Everyday layperson language is most appropriate to help a participant make an informed decision about participation.

^{xxix} People receiving the PIS should not be left wondering, “How did the researcher get my name?” or “Why am I being invited and not others?” or “Does the researcher already know private information about me?” The means by which the researcher has identified and contacted the potential participant needs to be made clear, if it is not already clear from the context. Sample explanations of inclusion criteria in PIS: (a) The human resources department has forwarded this invitation to all employees who meet the researcher’s study criteria (i.e., have been with the organization at least 2 years and have transitioned into a managerial role within the past year); or (b) The researcher is inviting all attendees of the past year’s XYZ professional conference to be in the study; or (c) The researcher will be randomly selecting possible participants by approaching the residents of every 5th home in this neighborhood until 100 responses are obtained.

^{xxx} When the researcher is already known to the participant, the PIS must include written assurance that declining or discontinuing will not negatively impact the participant’s relationship with the researcher or (if applicable) the invitee’s access to services.

^{xxxi} Provide an estimate (in minutes or hours) of each component of data collection (e.g., survey, interview, memberchecking, etc.)

^{xxxii} Describe only the possible harms that go beyond the risks of daily life.

^{xxxiii} For most social science studies, it is appropriate to state that there are no particular direct benefits to the individual. In this case, just present the benefits to society.

^{xxxiv} The PIS should explain that the research report will not include names and that the data will not be used for any purposes other than research. It is not always clear to participants how a research interview is different from a journalistic interview, in which informants might be named. So the PIS should also describe any coding system that will permit the researcher to not use names. For sensitive interviews, the researcher might also want to assure participants that recordings will be destroyed immediately after transcription.

^{xxxv} The consent forms/process should not ask a participant to waive any legal rights.

^{xxxvi} Vulnerable participants include children, clinic patients, prisoners, military personnel, facility residents, anyone over whom the researcher holds authority (e.g., students, subordinates), anyone who might feel undue pressure to participate in the study, and any individuals with severe enough mental disabilities to interfere with capacity to consent to the study. Pregnant women (and their unborn children) are only considered a vulnerable population when a study involves physically risky data collection.

^{xxxvii} Targeted recruitment of vulnerable participants can only be approved when the ethics committee determines that the study’s benefits justify its risks/costs.

^{xxxviii} A researcher with a dual role must use anonymous surveys or some other method that permits potential participants to opt out without fear of negative consequences. Patients, students, and subordinates of the researcher need explicit assurance that their decision about participation will in no way impact their ongoing relationship with the researcher.

^{xxxix} Any limits to confidentiality (i.e., duty to report) must be mentioned in the participant information sheet (PIS).